
Comparative Assessment of Job Satisfaction among Frontline Health Care Workers in a Tertiary Hospital in South East Nigeria

Justice Mgbecheta¹, Kelechi Onyenemezu², Chukwuemelie Okeke³, John Ubah⁴, Tobechukwu Ezike⁵, Queeneth Edwards⁶

¹Department of Community Medicine, Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital, Nnewi, Nigeria

^{2,5} College of Public Health, East Tennessee State University, USA

³Internal Medicine Department, Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital, Nnewi, Nigeria

⁴Royal Wolverhampton NHS Trust, Wolverhampton, UK

⁶Idara Clinic, Abuja, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

Background: Job satisfaction cuts across facets of mental perception and responses individuals make towards their jobs. They include cognitive, affective, and behavioral components. In light of reducing workforce in the Nigerian healthcare, this study was aimed at comparing the outlook of job satisfaction among healthcare workers in Nnamdi Azikiwe University teaching Hospital, Nnewi, Nigeria.

Methods: It was a cross-sectional study design with a sample size of 281 healthcare personnel consisting of doctors, nurses, medical laboratory scientists, pharmacists, physiotherapists, and radiographers using a structured, self-administered questionnaire. The data was analyzed using SPSS version 20. Statistical significance was set at $p \leq 0.05$.

Results: The study showed that Radiographers and Physiotherapists averagely had the best job satisfaction scores in comparison to other healthcare personnel. Doctors and Nurses were noted to have the worst average scores in relation to other personnel.

Conclusion: The disparity in job satisfaction among different professional cadres may be a reflection of disproportionate work expectations, outlooks, and rewards experienced by different professionals in the course of their duties. Favorable and unfavorable work environments and policies may be weighted differently in the work experience of different professionals.

KEYWORDS: Healthcare workers, Job satisfaction, Occupational Health.

1. INTRODUCTION

Until recently, little attention has been paid to the psychological effects of the working environment in Nigeria. The advent of new interest in occupational health psychology (OHP) is changing this narrative and has improved the understanding of the interrelationship between work environment and mental health. Job satisfaction is a wholesome psychological response by an individual to his job in terms of cognitive, affective, and behavioral dimensions. It is a positive outlook toward one's official duty and is useful in assessing employees' expectations and desires.^{1, 2, 3} Ng and Feldman in a meta-analytic review, found a positive though weak, relationship between age and overall, intrinsic, and extrinsic job satisfactions. However, when controlling for organizational tenure, the relationship between age and intrinsic satisfaction increased, and the relationship between age and overall and extrinsic satisfaction decreased.⁴ Drabe *et.al*, found that both intrinsic and extrinsic job characteristics are more predictive of younger employee job satisfaction, while job satisfaction for older employees was related to establishing good colleague relationships. Also, the impact of age on the relationship between job insecurity and job satisfaction may be higher for older workers when job insecurity is related to retirement concerns.^{5, 45} In the healthcare context, good job satisfaction among workers has been linked to several positive health outcomes.⁶ Evidence suggests that nurses' job satisfaction in turn affects patient satisfaction and the quality of patient care,^{7,8} and that good human resource management makes a difference in the hospital setting⁹ and even reduces mortality.¹⁰ A positive correlation between nurses' job satisfaction and retention has been established.^{11,12} A study among pharmacists showed that females had a higher mean job satisfaction than males.¹³ The lack of a global definition of job satisfaction has led to the development of multiple questionnaires for measuring job satisfaction with some of the researchers developing their own questionnaires to investigate job satisfaction and others using previously developed ones. These often reflect the theme upon which researchers choose to investigate the subject and tend to differ in their psychometric quality. The product of this inconsistency is the lack of a consensus as to a satisfactory measure on which different works can be

Comparative Assessment of Job Satisfaction among Frontline Health Care Workers in a Tertiary Hospital in South East Nigeria

compared. In the wake of a massive exodus of health personnel from the pool of the Nigerian healthcare service, this work is timely and does not attempt to reinvent the wheel as there is a paucity of available literature in this field of study in Nigeria. The work is aimed at comparing the job satisfaction of healthcare personnel in relation to one another.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Study setting

The study was conducted at Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital (NAUTH), Nnewi, with an estimated staff strength of 2700 including frontline health workers and auxiliary staff.

2.2 Study Design

It was a cross-sectional study carried out between 1st April to 31st May, 2019 using a stratified random sampling technique. The data were obtained with the aid of an adapted Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ)¹⁴ which was a structured, and self-administered questionnaire.

2.3 Study Population

The study population included doctors, nurses, pharmacists, physiotherapists, radiographers, and medical laboratory scientists working in Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital, Nnewi.

2.3.1 Inclusion Criteria

All members of the study population were included in the study.

2.3.2 Exclusion Criteria

Staff members who were not frontline healthcare workers were excluded from the study.

The study also excluded frontline healthcare workers who were on leave of work all through the duration of the study.

2.4 Study Instrument

The first part of the questionnaire was used to assess the socio-demographic characteristics of the participants.

In the second part of the questionnaire, the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ) short form was adapted for use in gathering data about the job satisfaction of the participants. The MSQ consists of 20 items and uses a 5-point Likert-type response format. Each response to the 20 questions of the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Questionnaire was scored from 1 to 5 as follows: 1 for very dissatisfied, 2 for dissatisfied, 3 for can't decide, 4 for satisfied, and 5 for very satisfied. The general job satisfaction score is derived as a sum of the score of the 20 responses. The intrinsic satisfaction score was derived from a summation of the scores for questions 1, 2, 3, 4, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 15, 16, and 20. The extrinsic satisfaction score was derived from a summation of the scores for questions 5, 6, 12, 13, 14, and 19. Questions 18 and 19 are neither assessed in the extrinsic nor intrinsic domain.

2.5 Data Analysis

The data was analyzed using SPSS version 20 and presented in tables. Categorical data were presented in frequencies and proportions and numerical variables were expressed in mean and standard deviation. Using dummy variables, multiple linear regression analysis was used to assess the domains of job satisfaction score of respondents according to profession with adjustment for age, gender, marital status, and number of years post-qualification. The level of significance was set at $p \leq 0.05$.

3. RESULTS

A total of 281 filled questionnaires were retrieved out of the 366 administered, giving a response rate of 77%. The 281 respondents comprised 125 males (44.5%) and 156 females (55.5%). 244 participants reported their age and it ranged from 18 to 58 years giving a mean age of 28.13 ± 6.83 years.

Table 3.1. Shows the Socio-demographic characteristics of the participants

GENDER	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)	Mean	SD
Male	125	44.5		
Female	156	55.5		
AGE(years)			28.13	6.83
18-25	109	44.7		
26-35	98	40.2		
36-45	29	11.9		
46-55	7	2.9		
56-65	1	0.4		
65 and above	0	0		

Comparative Assessment of Job Satisfaction among Frontline Health Care Workers in a Tertiary Hospital in South East Nigeria

MARITAL STATUS		
Single	201	71.8
Married	78	27.9
Widowed	1	0.3
Divorced	0	0
NUMBER OF CHILDREN		
None	206	73.6
1-2	41	14.6
3-4	23	8.2
5-6	9	3.2
6 and above	1	0.4
ANY CHILD BELOW THE AGE OF 5		
Yes	64	22.8
No	217	77.2
CURRENTLY LIVING WITH FAMILY		
Yes	112	39.9
No	169	60.1
AVERAGE TIME TO WORK(minutes)		
<5	43	15.3
6-15	113	40.2
16-30	55	19.6
31-60	20	7.1
60 and above	50	17.8
YEARS POST QUALIFICATION		
<3	193	68.7
3-5	25	8.9
6-10	31	11.0
10 and above	32	11.4
JOB CATEGORY		
Doctor	114	40.6
Nurse	58	20.6
Medical laboratory scientist	34	12.1
Pharmacist	28	10.0
Physiotherapist	18	6.4
Radiographer	29	10.3
QUALITY OF WORKING FACILITY		
Excellent	10	3.6
Very good	22	7.9
Good	169	60.4
Bad	79	28.2

114(40.6%) were Doctors, 58(20.6%) were Nurses, 34(12.1%) were Medical Laboratory Scientists,28(10.0%) were Pharmacists,18(6.4%) were Physiotherapists, and 29(10.3%) were Radiographers. 201 (71.8%) respondents were single, 78 (27.9%) were married, and 1 (0.3%) was widowed. 74 (28.2%) of the respondents have at least a child while 64 (22.8%) have at least one child below the age of 5 years. 169 (60.1%) live away with from their families and 112 (39.9%) live with their families. 43 (15.3%) spend less than 5 minutes from home to work daily. 113 (40.2%) spend 6-15 minutes, while 125(44.5%) spend at least 16 minutes

Comparative Assessment of Job Satisfaction among Frontline Health Care Workers in a Tertiary Hospital in South East Nigeria

on commute to work. 193 (68.7%) had less than three years of experience. 79 (28.2%) had unfavorable appraisal of the quality of their working facilities.

Table 3.2 shows the frequency of responses to the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Questionnaire

Response	Frequency(N)	Percentage (%)
1. Able to keep busy at all times.		
Very dissatisfied	26	9.3
Dissatisfied	37	13.2
Can't decide	81	28.8
Satisfied	122	43.4
Very satisfied	15	5.3
Total	281	100
2. The chance to work alone on the job.		
Very dissatisfied	14	5.0
Dissatisfied	65	23.1
Can't decide	87	31.0
Satisfied	102	36.3
Very satisfied	36.3	4.6
Total	281	100
3. The chance to do different things from time to time.		
Very dissatisfied	14	5.0
Dissatisfied	45	16.0
Can't decide	57	20.3
Satisfied	139	49.5
Very satisfied	26	9.3
Total	281	100
4. The chance to be "somebody" in the community.		
Very dissatisfied	8	2.8
Dissatisfied	32	11.4
Can't decide	51	18.1
Satisfied	112	39.9
Very satisfied	78	27.8
Total	281	100
5. The way my boss handles his/her workers.		
Very dissatisfied	25	8.9
Dissatisfied	47	16.7
Can't decide	80	28.5
Satisfied	111	39.5
Very satisfied	18	6.4
Total	281	100
6. The competence of my supervisors in making decisions.		
Very dissatisfied	13	4.6
Dissatisfied	24	8.5
Can't decide	65	23.1
Satisfied	153	54.4
Very satisfied	26	9.3
Total	281	100
7. Being able to do things that don't go against my conscience.		
Very dissatisfied	12	4.3
Dissatisfied	42	14.9
Can't decide	60	21.4
Satisfied	124	44.1
Very satisfied	43	15.3
Total	281	100
8. The way my job provides for steady employment.		

Comparative Assessment of Job Satisfaction among Frontline Health Care Workers in a Tertiary Hospital in South East Nigeria

Very dissatisfied	24	8.5
Dissatisfied	51	18.1
Can't decide	78	27.8
Satisfied	94	33.5
Very satisfied	34	12.1
Total	281	100

9. The chance to do things for other people.

Very dissatisfied	4	1.4
Dissatisfied	22	7.8
Can't decide	44	15.7
Satisfied	146	52.0
Very satisfied	65	23.1
Total	281	100

10. The chance to tell people what to do.

Very dissatisfied	5	1.8
Dissatisfied	19	6.8
Can't decide	83	29.5
Satisfied	133	47.3
Very satisfied	41	14.6
Total	281	100

11. The chance to do something that makes use of my abilities.

Very dissatisfied	9	3.2
Dissatisfied	38	13.5
Can't decide	59	21.0
Satisfied	131	46.6
Very satisfied	44	15.7
Total	281	100

12. The way company policies are put into place.

Very dissatisfied	41	14.6
Dissatisfied	96	34.2
Can't decide	81	28.8
Satisfied	55	19.6
Very satisfied	8	2.8
Total	281	100

13. My pay and the amount of work I do.

Very dissatisfied	76	27.0
Dissatisfied	73	26.0
Can't decide	49	17.4
Satisfied	75	26.7
Very satisfied	8	2.8
Total	281	100

14. The chance for advancement on this job.

Very dissatisfied	16	5.7
Dissatisfied	55	19.6
Can't decide	75	26.7
Satisfied	106	37.7
Very satisfied	29	10.3
Total	281	100

15. The freedom to use my own Judgment.

Very dissatisfied	11	3.9
Dissatisfied	49	17.4
Can't decide	96	34.2
Satisfied	113	40.2
Very satisfied	12	4.3
Total	281	100

16. The Chance to try my own methods of doing the job.

Very dissatisfied	10	3.6
Dissatisfied	57	20.3
Can't decide	93	33.1
Satisfied	101	35.9
Very satisfied	20	7.1
Total	281	100

17. The working conditions.

Very dissatisfied	80	28.5
Dissatisfied	85	30.2
Can't decide	61	21.7
Satisfied	45	16.0
Very satisfied	10	3.6
Total	281	100

18. The way my co-workers get along with each other.

Very dissatisfied	15	5.3
Dissatisfied	37	13.2
Can't decide	77	27.4
Satisfied	129	45.9
Very satisfied	23	8.2
Total	281	100

19. The praise I get for doing a good job.

Very dissatisfied	15	5.3
Dissatisfied	49	17.4
Can't decide	76	27.0
Satisfied	107	38.1
Very satisfied	34	12.1
Total	281	100

20. The feeling of accomplishment I get from the job.

Very dissatisfied	13	4.6
Dissatisfied	32	11.4
Can't decide	50	17.8
Satisfied	121	43.1
Very satisfied	34	23.1
Total	281	100

Forty-three percent (43.4%) of respondents were satisfied with being able to keep busy at work. Thirty-six percent (36.3%) were satisfied with the chance to work alone on the job, whereas twenty-three (23.1%) were dissatisfied. Forty-nine percent (49.5%) of respondents were satisfied with the chance to do different things from time to time. Up to 39.9% of respondents were satisfied with how their job gives them a chance to be “somebody” in the community. Thirty-nine percent (39.5%) of respondents were dissatisfied with the way their boss handles his/her workers, whereas 8.9% were very dissatisfied. Fifty-four percent (54.4%) of respondents were satisfied with the competence of their supervisors in making decisions, while another 9.3% were very satisfied. Forty-four percent (44.1%) of respondents were satisfied with being able to do things that don't go against their conscience, while another 15.3% were very satisfied. Thirty-three percent (33.5%) of respondents were satisfied with the way their job provides for steady employment, whereas 18.1% were dissatisfied. Majority (52%) of respondents were satisfied with the chance to do things for other people, while another 23.1% were very satisfied. Forty-seven percent (47.3%) of participants were satisfied with how their job provides the chance to tell people what to do. With regards to the chance to do something that makes use of their abilities, 46.6% were satisfied. When asked about the way company policies are put into place, majority (34.2%) were dissatisfied while another 14.6% were very dissatisfied. When asked to compare their pay and the amount of work they do, majority (53.3%) of respondents were either very dissatisfied or dissatisfied. Thirty-seven percent (37.7%) of respondents were satisfied with the chance for advancement in their job. As regard freedom to use their own judgment while working, 40.2% of respondents were satisfied. Thirty-five percent (35%) of respondents were satisfied with the chance to use their own method. Thirty percent (30%) of respondents were dissatisfied with their working conditions. Forty-five percent (45.9%) of respondents were satisfied with the way their co-workers get along with each other. Thirty eight percent (38.1%) of respondents were satisfied with the praise they get for a good job. Majority (46.2%) of respondents were either satisfied or very satisfied with the feeling of accomplishment they get from the job.

Table 3.3 shows multiple linear regression analyses of job satisfaction scores of individual professions with adjustment for age, gender, marital status, and post-qualification duration.

	General Satisfaction	p-value	Intrinsic Satisfaction	p-value	Extrinsic satisfaction	p-value
Radiographers	6.596	0.01	5.885	0.002	4.369	<0.001
Physiotherapists	11.553	<0.001	0.467	0.752	1.596	0.080
Pharmacists	2.800	0.255	3.066	0.046	2.102	0.027
Med Lab Scientists	4.644	0.051	2.083	0.145	1.411	0.110
Nurses	-4.511	0.027	-1.738	0.158	-2.147	0.005
Doctors	-5.927	<0.001	-2.713	0.004	-1.892	0.001

The average general, intrinsic, and extrinsic job satisfaction scores for Radiographers, Physiotherapists, Pharmacists, and Medical Laboratory Scientists individually were relatively higher in comparison to all others who were not in these professions while those of Nurses and Doctors were averagely lesser than those who were not.

4. DISCUSSION

Roughly equal proportions of males and females participated in the study. With a mean age of 28 years and more than two-thirds of respondents below the age of 35 years, a majority of the participants were within five years post-qualification, and most of the respondents were single. With adjustment for age, gender, marital status, and post-qualification duration, physiotherapists had the average highest general job satisfaction than other personnel and this was statistically significant. However, radiographers showed the average highest intrinsic and extrinsic job satisfaction scores than others. The finding was statistically significant as well. Conversely, doctors and nurses were shown to averagely score lesser in all domains of the assessment than other personnel with the doctors significantly scoring the least in the general and intrinsic satisfaction domains, while nurses averagely scored the least in the extrinsic domain relative to others. These findings could be due to differences in the perceptions and expectations of different healthcare professionals in terms of workload, work schedule, conduciveness of workplace, ease and effectiveness of work, remuneration relative to input, and job security.

Limitations of the Study

The study is limited by its small sample size but adequate stratification and randomization reduced selection bias.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Interest in employee job satisfaction benefits everyone involved. Healthcare workers will more likely tend to remain with their current employer if they have a good sense of job satisfaction. It is imperative, judging by the shortage of skilled manpower for health, that employers learn how to manage these often overworked and burnout workers to mitigate employee loss which impacts negatively on patient care. This study examined the relative differences in job satisfaction among frontline health professionals and brings to light the perception of these professionals. Administrators of healthcare and indeed all who consume healthcare services would play a key role in addressing the disparity in job satisfaction among health professionals. This study will help to lay a foundation for the assessment of job satisfaction among healthcare workers in Nigeria. Assessment of the level of job satisfaction is recommended so as to determine the gap of needs to be addressed. Following action, it will be imperative to study how relative job satisfaction changes with time among healthcare workers. Even more important will be to identify and investigate the effect of certain interventions on job satisfaction.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical approval was obtained from the Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital Ethics Committee. Informed consent was obtained from all participants in the study.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest

Funding

This study was solely sponsored by the authors from execution to publication.

REFERENCES

- 1) Mueller, Charles W., and McCloskey, Joanne C. "Nurses' Job Satisfaction: A Proposed Measure". *Nursing Research*.1990;39(2): 113-117
- 2) Weiss HM and Cropanzano R. "Affective Events Theory: a Theoretical Discussion of the Structure, Causes and Consequences of Affective Experiences at Work" In *Research in Organization Behavior: An Annual Series of Analytical Essays and Critical Reviews*.1996; pp. 1-74.

Comparative Assessment of Job Satisfaction among Frontline Health Care Workers in a Tertiary Hospital in South East Nigeria

- 3) Fisher, Cynthia D. "Why Do Lay People Believe That Satisfaction and Performance Are Correlated? Possible Sources of a Commonsense Theory". *Journal of Organizational Behavior*.2003; 24(6): 753-777.
- 4) Ng TW, Feldman DC. The relationships of age with job attitudes: a meta-analysis. *Pers. Psychol.* 2010; 63:677–718.
- 5) Drabe D, Hauff S, Richter NF. Job satisfaction in aging workforces: an analysis of the USA, Japan and Germany. *Int. J. Hum. Res. Manag.* 2015; 26:783–805.
- 6) Sunday JA, Omolola I, Mayowa AO .Job Satisfaction and Work Environment of Primary Health Care Nurses in Ekiti State, Nigeria: an Exploratory Study. *International Journal of Caring Sciences.* 2013; 6(3):531-541.
- 7) Aiken LH, Smith, H.L. and Lake, E.T. Lower Medicare Mortality among a Set of Hospitals Known for Good Nursing Care. *Medical Care.* 1994; 32(8): 771-787.
- 8) Aiken LH, Lake ET, Sochalski J and Sloane DM. Design of an Outcomes Study of the Organization of Hospital Aids Care .*Research in the Sociology of Health Care.*1997;14: 3-26.
- 9) Buchan M. What Difference Does ("Good") HRM Make? .*Human Resources for Health.*2004; 2(6).
- 10) West M, Guthrie J, Dawson J, Borrill C and Carter M. Reducing Patient Mortality in Hospitals: The Role of Human Resource Management .*Journal of Organizational Behaviour.*2006; 27: 983-1002.
- 11) Leveck ML and Jones CB. The Nursing Practice Environment, Staff Retention, and Quality of Care. *Research in Nursing and Health.*1996; 19(4): 331–343.
- 12) Molassiotis, A. and Haberman, M. Evaluation of Burnout and Job Satisfaction in Marrow Transplant Nurses.. *Cancer Nursing.*1996; 19(5): 360-367.
- 13) Manuel J C, Ioana P, and Patrick C.“Gender differences in the measurement of pharmacists’ job satisfaction”. *Hum Resour Health.* 2018; 16: 33.
- 14) Weiss D J, Dawis R, England W. and Lofquist H. Manual for the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire. Minnesota Studies in Vocational Rehabilitation, Minneapolis: University of Minnesota, Industrial Relations Center.1967; Vol. 22.